

ARCHAECHEMIS: TACKLING ARCHAEOLOGICAL ISSUES THROUGH CHEMISTRY

(ARQUEOLOGÍA; ARQUEOMETRÍA)

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Resumen

In the last years, Chemistry has become an important ally of Archaeology due to increasingly wider employment of analytical techniques in order to solve archaeological issues such as the ancient artefacts provenance, the construction phases of historical structures and the impact of past human activities on soils.

The ArchaeChemis unit of the University of Valencia was funded by Dr. Gianni Gallelo (Dep. of Prehistory, Archaeology and Ancient History) and Prof. Agustín Pastor García (Dep. of Analytical Chemistry) and it has been devoted to research in archaeology and cultural heritage since 2014 by employing spectroscopy and spectrometry techniques and developing new methods for the study of ancient materials.

The aim of this speech is to show some of the studies carried out by the ArchaeChemis unit in which Chemistry gave a fundamental support in order to answer to archaeological questions.